

Analysis of nickel oxide as a counter electrode for dye-sensitized solar cells using OghmaNano software

Nur Afiqah Hani Senin¹, Iskandar Dzulkarnain Rummaja¹, Muhammad Idzdihar Idris^{1,2},
Zul Atfyi Fauzan Mohammed Napiah^{1,2}, Radi Husin Ramlee², Marzaini Rashid³, Luke Bradley⁴

¹Faculty of Electronic and Computer Technology and Engineering, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM), Melaka, Malaysia

²Micro and Nano Electronic Research Group (MiNE), Faculty of Electronic and Computer Technology and Engineering,
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM), Melaka, Malaysia

³School of Physics, University Science Malaysia (USM), Penang, Malaysia

⁴Cyro-Electronics at School of Engineering, Newcastle University, Newcastle, United Kingdom

Article Info

Article history:

Received Sep 25, 2023

Revised Nov 27, 2023

Accepted Dec 7, 2023

Keywords:

Counter electrode

Doped nickel oxide

Dye sensitized solar cells

Thickness

Zinc oxide

ABSTRACT

Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs), a promising green technology, convert solar energy into electricity more cost-effectively than traditional solar cells. While platinum (Pt) is commonly used in DSSCs, its high cost and toxicity limit practical applications. Recent research aims to develop low-cost counter electrodes with high efficiency. Nickel oxide (NiO), a p-type semiconductor with a wide bandgap, good transmittance, and suitable work function, emerges as a potential alternative for counter electrode of DSSCs. In this work, DSSCs with NiO of thicknesses varying from 100 nm to 1000 nm were simulated to determine its influence on photovoltaic performance using OghmaNano software. The structure of simulated solar cells consists of NiO as counter electrode, zinc oxide (ZnO) as photoanode, N719 as dyes, electrolyte as charge carrier transport, and fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) as a contact layer. There are five data of NiO used as an active layer. From the simulation results, NiO-doped gold exhibits the highest power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 15.95% at a thickness of 700 nm, while pure NiO shows the lowest PCE with 4.53% at a thickness of 600 nm. These results have demonstrated that NiO can replace Pt as a counter electrode for DSSCs and doping plays a vital role in increasing efficiency.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](#) license.

Corresponding Author:

Muhammad Idzdihar Idris

Faculty of Electronic and Computer Technology and Engineering,

Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM)

St. Hang Tuah Jaya, 76100 Durian Tunggal, Melaka, Malaysia

Email: idzdihar@utem.edu.my

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many potentials uses for dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC); thus, it has been the subject of intense study over the past decade. These uses vary from renewable energy and flexibility to alternative energy sources. Within inorganic DSSCs, the generation of electrical current can be summarized into 4 key steps: i) Excitons are created when light photons are absorbed; ii) Then, excitons diffuse at the donor-acceptor interface; iii) Subsequently, the exciton dissociates into charge carriers while relaxing with the help of charge carriers; and iv) All electrons and holes flow to their respective cathode and anode contacts where the process then repeats [1]-[3]. In DSSC, the counter electrode is an important layer as for example, in the redox electrolyte formed of iodine and iodide, the counter electrode's role is to transfer electrons from an external circuit to the tri-iodide and iodine [4]. (Pt) is typically used as a catalyst because of its high conductivity and

electrocatalytic properties, but it comes at a high cost when used on a large scale [5]. The RF magnetron co-sputtering method also prepared metal oxide bi-phase counter electrodes (Pt/NiO [6], [7] and Pt/TiO₂ [7]). However, high-efficiency Pt/NiO (or Pt/TiO₂) bi-phase counter electrodes require costly vacuum technology and precise process control. Currently, many researchers are focusing on p-type oxide semiconductors as hole transport layers or counter electrodes. This is because tandem photovoltaic devices combine p-type oxide cathodes with n-type oxide anodes, which can increase efficiency and decrease the cost of solar harvesting systems [8].

The primary concern regarding platinum pertains to its elevated cost, which renders it unfeasible for practical applications in real-world contexts. Therefore, this study introduces a novel solution for the counter electrode by employing NiO as a cost-effective substitute. The objective of this substitution is to improve the efficiency of dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) by using the advantageous properties of NiO, such as its cost-effective raw materials, excellent durability, and strong chemical stability, together with its promising electrical and optical characteristics [9]-[11]. Furthermore, NiO is a p-type, high-work function semiconductor with a bandgap of 3.6-4.0 eV [12]-[14]. NiO has previously been employed as an HTL in several prior studies to improve the performance of CdTe, organic, DSSC, and perovskite solar cells [14]-[17]. In addition, an interfacial layer (or HTL) is often inserted between the ITO anode and the p-type layers to collect the generated holes and prevent minority carrier injection (electrons) [18]. However, NiO was used for DSSC counter electrodes. Guai *et al.* [19] demonstrated a DSSC with a sulfur-doped NiO counter electrode that achieved a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 5.04%. Then, Okumura *et al.* [20] achieved a PCE of 5.11% with a DSSC using NiO hybridized carbon film as the cathode. Wang *et al.* [21] achieved the highest PCE of 7.58% for NiO/PEDOT: PSS as the counter electrode. Maitra *et al.* [22] showed that using nickel-doped molybdenum oxide for the counter electrodes increased efficiency to 4.17%. However, DSSC counter electrodes made of NiO and conductive polymers have not been studied yet till today.

This paper simulates DSSCs using NiO with varying thickness as the counter electrode using OghmaNano software. The DSSCs with varying NiO thickness as a counter electrode were simulated using OghmaNano software to investigate the potential of the materials. The OghmaNano is a general-purpose tool for simulating optoelectronic and photovoltaic devices. This software uses finite differences algorithms to solve the drift-diffusion equations for electrons and holes within devices. The DSSCs internal structure consists of FTO/ZnO/N719/Electrolyte/NiO/FTO. The electrical stimulation only reaches the active layer, whereas, in this simulation, the active layer only focuses on NiO [23]-[29]. The thickness of NiO was varied from 100 nm to 1000 nm to determine the optimal thickness to achieving the best power conversion efficiency (PCE), open circuit voltage (Voc), short circuit current density (Jsc), and fill factor. The OghmaNano results that an optimal layer NiO is needed to maximize the PCE of the DSSC.

2. METHOD

2.1. OghmaNano simulation software

The OghmaNano simulation software is a general-purpose tool for simulating optoelectronics and photovoltaic devices based on a drift-diffusion base. The OghmaNano developed by Dr. Roderick Mackenzie of the University of Nottingham simulates several thin-film devices using drift-diffusion equations and other electrical and optical models. Organic LEDs and perovskite solar cells are examples of thin film technologies already integrated into the system. This work uses this model to simulate the electrical and optical characteristics of the active layer and is unique among similar programmes in that it gives non-experts the ability to create their own thin film devices from scratch. The software can simulate various phenomena, including JV curves, impedance spectroscopy, and ray tracing. The I-V and J-V graphs are displayed using simulation data to demonstrate the pattern of electron density when a voltage is applied to the simulated device. The significant aspects affecting its performance can be investigated to maximize the efficiency of organic solar cells in converting light to electricity. The OghmaNano programmed simulates various layer thicknesses of dye-sensitized solar cells and photons absorbed by the solar cells. The software manual contains a more detailed description of model.

2.2. Electrical model

The electrical simulation consists of 5 distinct layers. The layers are FTO/ZnO/N719/Electrolyte/NiO/FTO. OghmaNano simulated this dye-sensitized solar cell at various active layer thicknesses. Figure 1 illustrates all the layers in detail. The electrical stimulation only reaches the device's active layer, whereas the thickness only focuses on NiO in this simulation. As a result, the fill factor (FF) can be calculated using (1), where Jsc is located at the curve's simulation, and Voc is the maximum output voltage. The PCE (η) is given by (2), where Pin denotes the light's power density and Pout indicates the electric power produced by the bulk heterojunction solar device at its highest power point [30].

$$FF = \frac{V_{max}J_{max}}{V_{oc}J_{sc}} \quad (1)$$

$$\eta = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} = \frac{FF * V_{max}J_{max}}{P_{in}} \quad (2)$$

In OghmaNano material databases, the data for NiO, ZnO&N719, and the electrolyte are not provided. Therefore, five data (absorption and refractive index) for NiO from the previous research [23]- [34] were taken and used as an active layer to compare the (PCE). Since the data for the refractive index ZnO with N719 is unavailable, the refractive index from ZnO was used instead [35], [36]. The absorption coefficient (α) was determined using the Beer-Lambert relationship as stated in (3), where A is the absorbance and t is the thickness of the film [37]. The unit of thickness must be in meters to obtain α .

$$\alpha = 2.303A/t \quad (3)$$

Figure 1 shows the layer of the solar cells where fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) is the contact layer. FTO is a practical, transparent layer that absorbs UV light and transmits electrons [38]. The thickness of the active layer is critical in a solar cell, where the NiO layer is the material layer used for converting photons into electrons and holes [18].

Table 1 shows the layer thickness and type of layer for each layer of the simulated DSSCs. To study the effect of different types of NiO (NiO doped with La (1) and (2), NiO doped with gold, Co-doped with NiO, and NiO pure) as counter electrodes in DSSC, all layers were fixed at 100 nm. The thickness of the counter electrode was varied from 100 nm to 1000 nm with 100 nm step.

Table 2 shows the electrical parameters changed for layer ZnO&dye, electrolyte, and NiO. All the parameters were extracted from data in literature [39]-[41]. Since OghmaNano software cannot simulate the widest bandgap, the layer of ZnO&dye and electrolyte were also set as an active layer, but only the thickness of NiO was varied. Hence, the large bandgap makes the minority carriers go to zero. Due to the large band gap of ZnO&dye, the minority carrier concentration is neglected within the simulations.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the simulated DSSC

Table 1. Layer editor in OghmaNano simulation

Layer name	Thickness	Material	Layer Type
FTO	10^{-7}	FTO	Contact
ZnO&Dye	10^{-7}	ZnO&N719	Active layer
Electrolyte	10^{-7}	Electrolyte	Active layer
NiO	10^{-7} - 100^{-7}	NiO	Active layer
FTO	10^{-7}	FTO	Contact

Table 2. Electrical parameters used in OghmaNano simulation

Parameter	ZnO&Dye	Electrolyte	NiO
Electron mobility ($m^2v^{-1}s^{-1}$)	0.01 [40]	10-5 [41]	2.8e-05 [42]
Hole mobility ($m^2v^{-1}s^{-1}$)	0.0025 [40]	10-5 [41]	2.8e-05 [42]
Relative permittivity (au)	9 [40]	3.5 [41]	11.7 [38]
Number of traps (bands)	0	0	0
Electron affinity (eV)	3.9 [43]	3.79 [41]	1.64 [42]
Bandgap (eV)	2.37 [43]	1.6 [41]	3.8 [42]

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the research findings will be presented and a comprehensive discussion will be provided. The findings of this study are effectively communicated by employing various visual aids such as figures, graphs, tables, and other graphical representations [42], [43]. These visual aids are strategically utilized to improve the reader's understanding and interpretation of the results. The present discussion has been structured into various sub-sections in order to facilitate a comprehensive examination of the research findings, their implications, and any potential limitations that may arise.

3.1. Electrical simulation

This section discusses the results obtained from the simulation using OghmaNano software of dye-sensitized solar cells using NiO as a counter electrode. The simulation results were divided into the electrical and optical simulations. Different types of NiO, which are NiO doped with La (1) and (2) [44]-[46], NiO doped with gold, Co-doped with NiO, and pure NiO, were used in the simulation to observe how the different composition of the NiO layer influences the PCE, Voc, Jsc, and fill factor. As well as this, the impact of different thicknesses of NiO on the performance of DSSC was also investigated.

The data in Figure 2(a) show the effect of different thicknesses on the performance of various types of NiO on the PCE. As can be observed in Figure 2(a), NiO-doped gold has the highest PCE with 15.95%, followed with NiO doped La (1) at 13.77%, NiO-doped La (2) at 8.26%, Co-doped NiO at 5.23%, and lastly, pure NiO with 4.53%. In several earlier research publications, NiO has been employed as a high-temperature layer (HTL) to improve the performance of CdTe, organic, and perovskite solar cells [40]-[47].

The data in Figure 2(b) shows the current density, J as a function of applied voltage, V for DSSCs with the optimized thickness of the counter electrode. Table 3 summarizes the optimized parameters of Voc, Jsc, fill factor, and PCE effect for all DSSCs with different NiO types. As can be seen from the table, all solar cells have high open-circuit voltages (Voc) greater than 0.85 V. The optimized thickness of the counter electrode is around 600 and 700 nm. Gold and La-doped NiO counter electrodes exhibit relatively higher efficiency than Co-doped and pure NiO. These results agree with the experimental results reported where Gold-doped NiO [26]. The highest PCE is gold-doped NiO with 15.95% at 600 nm and lowest PCE is pure NiO, with 4.53% at 700 nm.

Figure 2. The result of PCE: (a) effect of NiO layer thickness on PCE and (b) J-V characteristic curve at maximum efficiency point

Table 3. The values of Voc, Jsc, FF, and PCE for the NiO

Material	Thickness	Jsc (mA/m ²)	Voc (V)	FF (%)	η (%)
Pure NiO	600	-52.808	0.987	0.869	4.533
Lanthanum-doped NiO (La: NiO) (a)	700	-160.72	0.102	0.837	13.77
Lanthanum-doped NiO (La: NiO) (b)	600	-97.54	1.003	0.844	8.2571
Gold-doped NiO (Gold: NiO)	700	-194.56	1.027	0.836	15.95

3.2. Optical simulation

The same device structure of dye-sensitized solar cell: FTO/ZnO&dye/electrolyte/NiO/FTO were used for the optical simulation by OghmaNano software to investigate the generation rate and absorbed photon

distribution with the DSSC. The highest PCE and the lowest PCE were compared in the optical simulation. Figure 3(a) show the generation rate profiles of gold doped NiO and Figure 3(b) show the pure NiO as an active layer at the optimized thickness of 700 and 600 nm, respectively. It is evident that the generation rate of gold-doped NiO DSSSC is higher compared to the pure NiO DSSC. Interestingly, the generation also occurs at the gold doped NiO interface.

Figure 3. Generation rate profiles of (a) gold: NiO and (b) pure NiO as an active layer at the optimized thickness of 700 nm and 600 nm, respectively

Figure 4(a) represents the absorbed photon distribution of NiO-doped gold at a thickness of 700 nm, corresponding to the maximum value of PCE. In the DSSC with a ZnO&dye thickness of 100 nm, the distribution of the absorbed photon is close to the electrodes. If photon energy exceeds the active layer's bandgap, charge carrier generation and collection potential increase, resulting in a higher fill factor. In a cell with an active area of 700 nm, most absorbed photons have wavelengths ranging from 300 nm to 500 nm. Since photons with longer wavelengths cannot bridge the bandgap, many absorbed photons are required to achieve optimal power conversion efficiency.

As we can see from Figure 4(b), this finding reveals that increasing active layer thickness enhances photon absorption in DSSC, while decreasing the PCE as the increased active layer thickness increases photon absorption and excitation, increasing the electron and hole density. The greater thickness of the active layer facilitates the extended movement of excitons from their generation point to eventual dissipation. However, within this denser structure, the risk of recombination is heightened due to the restricted mobility of ions, electrons, and holes. Consequently, it is imperative to strike a delicate equilibrium between these contrasting effects. The findings from our simulations indicate that augmenting the thickness of NiO contributes to an enhancement in the overall performance of DSSC. The photon absorption is maximal near the electrode, with the smallest reflective value and maximum in the centre of the active layer [48].

The tunable energy bandgap interface in the solar cell allows the photovoltaic layer to produce electron-hole pairs. The ZnO&dye layer attracts the electrons, while the NiO layer attracts the holes [49]. As a consequence of this, it is important to emphasize once more that the number density of available photons passing through the layer can be affected by the following factors: (1) absorbed photons in all previous or same layers; (2) photons successfully converted into free carriers in all previous layers; and (3) reflected photons from the ITO surface.

Figure 4. Absorbed photon distribution in an active region of: (a) gold-doped NiO and (b) pure NiO as an active layer at the optimized thickness of 700 and 600 nm, respectively

4. CONCLUSION

DSSCs structure of FTO/ZnO&N719/Electrolyte/NiO/FTO was simulated using OghmaNano simulation software. The effect of different types of NiO was studied with varying thicknesses from 100 nm to 1000 nm to find the highest efficiency. From the simulation results, gold-doped NiO has the best power conversion efficiency of 15.9% compared a PCE of 4.53% for pure NiO. The recombination rate of electron pairs and holes was discovered to depend on the thickness of the active layer. Therefore, gold was the best material for the counter electrode to be doped with NiO to achieve the best DSSC efficiency.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Ministry of Higher Education Malaysia and Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka through the Fundamental Research Grant Scheme with Project No FRGS/1/2022/TK08/UTEM/02/6. Author also acknowledges the provider of free version of OghmaNano software.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Pala *et al.*, "Analysis and design optimization of organic dye sensitized solar cell based on simulation," *AIP Conference Proceedings*, vol. 1837, 2017, doi: 10.1063/1.4982082.

- [2] K. Nithyanandam and R. Pitchumani, "Analysis and design of dye-sensitized solar cell," *Solar Energy*, vol. 86, no. 1, pp. 351–368, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2011.10.009.
- [3] B. O'Regan and M. Grätzel, "A low-cost, high-efficiency solar cell based on dye-sensitized colloidal TiO₂ films," *Nature*, vol. 353, no. 6346, pp. 737–740, 1991, doi: 10.1038/353737a0.
- [4] "IEEE Malaysia Section. Electron Devices Chapter, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, and IEEE Electron Devices Society," *ICSE 2020 : 2020 IEEE International Conference on Semiconductor Electronics : proceedings : virtual conference, 28-29 July 2020, Kuala Lumpur*.
- [5] M. Wu and T. Ma, "Platinum-free catalysts as counter electrodes in dye-sensitized solar cells," *ChemSusChem*, vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 1343–1357, 2012, doi: 10.1002/cssc.201100676.
- [6] S. S. Kim, K. W. Park, J. H. Yum, and Y. E. Sung, "Pt-NiO nanophase electrodes for dye-sensitized solar cells," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 90, no. 3, pp. 283–290, 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2005.03.015.
- [7] S. S. Kim, K. W. Park, J. H. Yum, and Y. E. Sung, "Dye-sensitized solar cells with Pt-NiO and Pt-TiO₂ biphasic counter electrodes," *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, vol. 189, no. 2–3, pp. 301–306, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.jphotochem.2007.02.019.
- [8] A. Nattestad *et al.*, "Highly efficient photocathodes for dye-sensitized tandem solar cells," *Nature Materials*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 31–35, 2010, doi: 10.1038/nmat2588.
- [9] Z. Liu *et al.*, "Nickel oxide nanoparticles for efficient hole transport in p-i-n and n-i-p perovskite solar cells," *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, vol. 5, no. 14, pp. 6597–6605, 2017, doi: 10.1039/c7ta01593c.
- [10] Q. X. Xia *et al.*, "A facile synthesis method of hierarchically porous NiO nanosheets," *Materials Letters*, vol. 69, pp. 69–71, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.matlet.2011.11.063.
- [11] S. Muniandy, M. I. Bin Idris, Z. A. F. B. M. Napiah, and M. Rashid, "The effect of pH level and annealing temperature on NiO thin films as Hole Transport Material in Inverted Perovskite Solar Cells," *IEEE International Conference on Semiconductor Electronics, Proceedings, ICSE*, vol. 2022-Augus, pp. 13–16, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ICSE56004.2022.9863126.
- [12] S. H. Lin, F. R. Chen, and J. J. Kai, "Electrochromic properties of nano-structured nickel oxide thin film prepared by spray pyrolysis method," *Applied Surface Science*, vol. 254, no. 7, pp. 2017–2022, 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2007.08.029.
- [13] M. I. Hossain, F. H. Alharbi, and N. Tabet, "Copper oxide as inorganic hole transport material for lead halide perovskite based solar cells," *Solar Energy*, vol. 120, pp. 370–380, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2015.07.040.
- [14] L. K. Jagadamma, O. Blaszczyk, M. T. Sajjad, A. Ruseckas, and I. D. W. Samuel, "Efficient indoor p-i-n hybrid perovskite solar cells using low temperature solution processed NiO as hole extraction layers," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 201, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2019.110071.
- [15] H. M. Yates, J. L. Hodgkinson, S. M. P. Meroni, D. Richards, and T. M. Watson, "Flame Assisted Chemical Vapour Deposition of NiO hole transport layers for planar perovskite cells," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 385, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.surfcoat.2020.125423.
- [16] M. Szindler, M. M. Szindler, L. A. Dobrzanski, and T. Jung, "NiO nanoparticles prepared by the sol-gel method for a dye sensitized solar cell applications," *Archives of Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 92, no. 1, pp. 15–21, 2018, doi: 10.5604/01.3001.0012.5507.
- [17] K. X. Steirer *et al.*, "Solution deposited NiO thin-films as hole transport layers in organic photovoltaics," *Organic Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 8, pp. 1414–1418, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.orgel.2010.05.008.
- [18] A. C. Nkele *et al.*, "The use of nickel oxide as a hole transport material in perovskite solar cell configuration: Achieving a high performance and stable device," *International Journal of Energy Research*, vol. 44, no. 13, pp. 9839–9863, 2020, doi: 10.1002/er.5563.
- [19] G. H. Guai, M. Y. Lei, C. M. Ng, and C. M. Li, "Sulfur-Doped Nickel Oxide Thin Film as an Alternative to Pt for Dye-Sensitized Solar Cell Counter Electrodes," *Advanced Energy Materials*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 334–338, Mar. 2012, doi: 10.1002/aenm.201100582.
- [20] T. Okumura, T. Sugiyo, T. Inoue, M. Ikegami, and T. Miyasaka, "Nickel Oxide Hybridized Carbon Film as an Efficient Mesoscopic Cathode for Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells," *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, vol. 160, no. 3, pp. H155–H159, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1149/2.029303jes.
- [21] H. Wang, W. Wei, and Y. H. Hu, "NiO as an Efficient Counter Electrode Catalyst for Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells," *Topics in Catalysis*, vol. 57, no. 6–9, pp. 607–611, Apr. 2014, doi: 10.1007/s11244-013-0218-8.
- [22] S. Maitra, S. Pal, S. Datta, T. Maitra, B. Dutta, and S. Roy, "Nickel doped molybdenum oxide thin film counter electrodes as a low-cost replacement for platinum in dye sensitized solar cells," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 39, pp. 1856–1861, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.07.531.
- [23] C. Mrabet, M. Ben Amor, A. Boukhachem, M. Amlouk, and T. Manoubi, "Physical properties of La-doped NiO sprayed thin films for optoelectronic and sensor applications," *Ceramics International*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 5963–5978, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2015.12.144.
- [24] V. Ganesh, L. Hariitha, M. A. Manthrammel, M. Shkir, and S. AlFaify, "An impact of La doping content on physical properties of NiO films facily casted through spin-coater for optoelectronics," *Physica B: Condensed Matter*, vol. 582, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.physb.2019.411955.
- [25] A. A. Al-Ghamdi, W. E. Mahmoud, S. J. Yagmour, and F. M. Al-Marzouki, "Structure and optical properties of nanocrystalline NiO thin film synthesized by sol-gel spin-coating method," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, vol. 486, no. 1–2, pp. 9–13, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2009.06.139.
- [26] M. M. A. Hussein and A. H. A. Jalaukhan, "An investigation of optical qualities of nickel oxide thin films doped with gold nanoparticles by thermal evaporation process," *International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering Research and Development*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 353–358, 2018, doi: 10.24247/ijmperdoct201840.
- [27] R. S. Kate, S. C. Bulakhe, and R. J. Deokate, "Co doping effect on structural and optical properties of nickel oxide (NiO) thin films via spray pyrolysis," *Optical and Quantum Electronics*, vol. 51, no. 10, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s11082-019-2026-2.
- [28] P. Wang, S. M. Zakeeruddin, J.-E. Moser, R. Humphry-Baker, and M. Grätzel, "A Solvent-Free, SeCN - / (SeCN) 3 - Based Ionic Liquid Electrolyte for High-Efficiency Dye-Sensitized Nanocrystalline Solar Cells," *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, vol. 126, no. 23, pp. 7164–7165, Jun. 2004, doi: 10.1021/ja048472r.
- [29] H. J. M. Al-Agealy *et al.*, "Theoretical study of electronic transfer current rate at dye-sensitized solar cells," *AIP Conference Proceedings*, vol. 1968, 2018, doi: 10.1063/1.5039242.
- [30] N. Rastogi, N. Singh, and S. Saxena, "Analysis of Organic Photovoltaic Device at Different Series Resistances," *Universal Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 83–87, 2017, doi: 10.13189/ujms.2017.050401.
- [31] H. Wang, W. Wei, and Y. H. Hu, "NiO as an efficient counter electrode catalyst for dye-sensitized solar cells," *Topics in Catalysis*, vol. 57, no. 6–9, pp. 607–611, 2014, doi: 10.1007/s11244-013-0218-8.

- [32] J. Patwari *et al.*, "Inversion of activity in DSSC for TiO₂ and ZnO photo-anodes depending on the choice of sensitizer and carrier dynamics," *Journal of Luminescence*, vol. 207, pp. 169–176, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jlumin.2018.11.012.
- [33] X. Zhang, C. Li, and Q. Ji, "Preparation of Electrode of Copper-Nickel Composite Material and Its Capacitance Performance," *World Journal of Nano Science and Engineering*, vol. 06, no. 04, pp. 165–176, 2016, doi: 10.4236/wjnse.2016.64015.
- [34] B. Kolev and V. Todorieva, "Solar Electricity Power Station Building. A Pre-liminary Project Investigation for 'PIRIN TEX LTD.' - Gotze Delchgeu Using," *Faculty of Mathematics & Natural Science – FMNS*, 2009.
- [35] S. Muhammad, A. T. Nomaan, M. I. Idris, and M. Rashid, "Structural, optical and electrical investigation of low-temperature processed zinc oxide quantum dots based thin films using precipitation-spin coating on flexible substrates," *Physica B: Condensed Matter*, vol. 635, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.physb.2022.413806.
- [36] A. T. Nomaan, A. A. Ahmed, N. M. Ahmed, M. I. Idris, M. R. Hashim, and M. Rashid, "ZnO quantum dot based thin films as promising electron transport layer: Influence of surface-to-volume ratio on the photoelectric properties," *Ceramics International*, vol. 47, no. 9, pp. 12397–12409, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2021.01.094.
- [37] K. Nama Manjunatha and S. Paul, "Investigation of optical properties of nickel oxide thin films deposited on different substrates," *Applied Surface Science*, vol. 352, pp. 10–15, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2015.03.092.
- [38] H. Slimani *et al.*, "Growth of ZnO nanorods on FTO glass substrate," *Materials Research Express*, vol. 7, no. 2, 2020, doi: 10.1088/2053-1591/ab727b.
- [39] K. Sobayel *et al.*, "Numerical modeling on prospective buffer layers for tungsten di-sulfide (WS₂) solar cells by scaps-1D," *Chalcogenide Letters*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 307–315, 2018.
- [40] S. Ahmmed, A. Aktar, J. Hossain, and A. B. M. Ismail, "Enhancing the open circuit voltage of the SnS based heterojunction solar cell using NiO HTL," *Solar Energy*, vol. 207, pp. 693–702, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2020.07.003.
- [41] M. S. Shamna, K. S. Nithya, and K. S. Sudheer, "Simulation and optimization of CH₃NH₃SnI₃ based inverted perovskite solar cell with NiO as Hole transport material," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 33, pp. 1246–1251, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.03.488.
- [42] F. Jahantigh and M. J. Safikhani, "The effect of HTM on the performance of solid-state dye-sensitized solar cells (SDSSCs): a SCAPS-1D simulation study," *Applied Physics A*, vol. 125, no. 4, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00339-019-2582-0.
- [43] J. R. Manders *et al.*, "Solution-processed nickel oxide hole transport layers in high efficiency polymer photovoltaic cells," *Advanced Functional Materials*, vol. 23, no. 23, pp. 2993–3001, 2013, doi: 10.1002/adfm.201202269.
- [44] P. Solanki, M. Vala, D. Dhruv, C. R. Savaliya, J. H. Markna, and B. Kataria, "Ni doping effect on the temperature-dependent dielectric properties and ac conductivity of polycrystalline GdMn_{1-x}Ni_xO₃ ceramics," *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, vol. 34, no. 19, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10854-023-10903-y.
- [45] R. Kajal, A. Kandasami, B. Kataria, P. Solanki, and D. Mohan, "Structural, optical, and dielectric characteristics of pulsed laser deposited SnO₂-TiO₂ composite thin films," *Physica Scripta*, vol. 98, no. 8, 2023, doi: 10.1088/1402-4896/ace569.
- [46] J. H. Markna and P. K. Rathod, "Review on the efficiency of quantum dot sensitized solar cell: Insights into photoanodes and QD sensitizers," *Dyes and Pigments*, vol. 199, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.dyepig.2022.110094.
- [47] J. Kim, B. Lee, Y. J. Kim, and S. W. Hwang, "Enhancement of Dye-sensitized Solar Cells Efficiency Using Graphene Quantum Dots as Photoanode," *Bulletin of the Korean Chemical Society*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 56–61, 2019, doi: 10.1002/bkcs.11664.
- [48] P. Sinha and P. Baghel, "Optical Simulation of Different Photoactive Layer Thickness on Organic Solar Cell," *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 1172–1177, 2020.
- [49] K. W. Kemp *et al.*, "Interface recombination in depleted heterojunction photovoltaics based on colloidal quantum dots," *Advance Energy Materials*, vol. 3, no. 7, pp. 917–922, 2013, doi: 10.1002/aenm.201201083.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Nur Afiqah Hani Senin is a graduate research assistant in the Faculty of Electronic and Computer Technology and Engineering at Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM) in Melaka, Malaysia. She holds a B.Eng. degree in electronic engineering from the same university and is currently pursuing an M.Sc. in electronic engineering at UTeM. Her research interests encompass semiconductor and solar cell technology. She can be contacted at email: m022210004@student.utm.edu.my.

Iskandar Dzulkarnain Rummaja is a graduate research assistant in the Faculty of Electronic and Computer Technology and Engineering at Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM) in Melaka, Malaysia. He holds a B.Eng. degree in electronic engineering technology (industrial electronics) from the same university and is currently pursuing an M.Sc. in electronic engineering at UTeM. His research interests are semiconductors, thin film, solar cells, renewable energy technology, internet of things (IoT) and artificial intelligence (AI). He can be contacted at email: iskandardzulkarnain964@gmail.com.

Muhammad Idzdihar Idris is a senior lecturer in Faculty of Electronic and Computer Technology and Engineering at Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM) in Melaka, Malaysia. He received his B.Eng. degree in electronic system engineering from Hiroshima University, Japan, M.sc in microelectronics from Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM) and Ph.D. in semiconductor devices from Newcastle University, United Kingdom in 2010, 2012 and 2018, respectively. His research interests are fabrication and characterization of semiconductor devices: MOSFET, solar cell, and gas sensor. He can be contacted at email: idzdihar@utem.edu.my.

Zul Atfy Fauzan Mohammed Napiah is a senior lecturer and serves as the Head of the Computer Engineering Department within the Faculty of Electronic and Computer Technology and Engineering at Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM) in Melaka, Malaysia. He earned his B.Eng. degree in electrical-electronics from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM), a M.Eng. in microelectronics from the same institution, and a Ph.D. in electronic engineering from Kanazawa University, Japan. His research interests are semiconductor devices, optoelectronics, and solar cells. He can be contacted at email: zulatfyi@utem.edu.my.

Radi Husin Ramlee is a lecturer in Faculty of Electronic and Computer Technology and Engineering at Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM) in Melaka, Malaysia. He received his B.Eng. (Hons) from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM) and M.Eng. in electrical from Imperial College London, United Kingdom. His research interests are microelectronics. He can be contacted at email: radihusin@utem.edu.my.

Marzaini Rashid is a lecturer at the school of physics, Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM), Malaysia. He earned his B.Eng. degree in electrical/electronic from Universiti Tenaga Malaysia (UNITEN), followed by an M.Sc. in physics from Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM) and a Ph.D. in optoelectronics from the University of Newcastle Upon Tyne, United Kingdom. His research focuses on nanostructured semiconductors and optoelectronic devices. He can be contacted at email: marzaini@usm.my.

Luke Bradley is a research associate at the University of Strathclyde within the Rolls Royce UTC group. He attained his bachelor of engineering in electrical and electronic engineering from Newcastle University in 2015. Following this, he focused on cryogenic power electronics during his professional tenure and completed his Ph.D. at Newcastle University in 2020. His areas of expertise encompass power electronics and circuits operating at cryogenic temperatures, power device simulations, and the application of microcontroller data logging. He can be contacted at email: luke.bradley@strath.ac.uk.